

BITCOIN PRICE PREDICTION USING ML

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Abstract— The decentralized digital currency known as Bitcoin has been used for trading and investment. To make wise judgments, traders and investors need to be able to predict the price of Bitcoin. In this paper, we attempted to predict the Bitcoin price using Machine Learning (ML) techniques. In particular, we utilized Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Random Forest Classifier (RFC) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) to predict the Bitcoin prices. These models are trained and evaluated using historical Bitcoin price data such as volume, open, high, and low prices. We have compared the performance of the ML algorithms with different parameters such as F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision. The outcomes of the experiments show that the performance of the XGBoost model is better than other ML algorithms. The accuracy of the XGBoost model is more than 92%. The XGBoost model also obtained better results in terms of precision, recall, and F1-Score.

Keywords—*Machine Learning, Bitcoin, Prediction, K-Nearest Neighbours, Long Short-Term Memory*

I. INTRODUCTION

Bitcoin, a cryptocurrency widely used for digital investment, operates on a decentralized system. Transactions with Bitcoins are straightforward as they are not tied to any specific country, allowing for ease of exchange across various markets known as bitcoin exchanges [2]. All Bitcoin operations handled by secure systems. Due to high volatility and price hike in Bitcoin, the traders and investors are interested in investing on Bitcoin. In order to get the profit, the traders and investors are attempted to forecast the price of the Bitcoin. Due to high volatility in Bitcoin, the investors lose their money in the market. The prediction of Bitcoin prices plays vital role to book profit in digital currency.

In order to predict the Bitcoin prices, the researcher uses different methodologies. Traditionally, traders used news, market sentiments, volume analysis, moving averages, support, resistance level, global economic states, etc. to predict the bitcoin prices. But these techniques do not provide accurate results. Thanks to ML prediction algorithms, which are able to perform prediction from historical data. ML algorithms are used in the different area such as student performance prediction, weather prediction, agriculture product price prediction, behavior prediction and so on [11]. Similarly, the

research has been initiated in order to predict the Bitcoin prices.

The goal of this study is to predict Bitcoin prices using ML techniques. In order to predict the Bitcoin prices, we have collected historical bitcoin data. Collected data are preprocessed and then we extracted necessary parameters to train the ML models. Dataset is divided into training data and testing data. Training data set is used to train the ML models. In order to detect Bitcoin prices, we applied different ML models such as LSTM, XGBoost, KNN, and RFC. These models are trained with the help of the collected dataset. The results show that the XGBoost classifier provides higher performance than other ML models. This research helps traders to utilize ML models to predict the price of bitcoin.

The paper is divided into five sections. Section 2 covers related work. Section 3 deals the overall system model. Section 4 presents a description of the process. The results and analysis are provided in Chapter 5, followed by the conclusions and future enhancements in Chapter 6.

II. RELATED WORK

Scholars have examined a variety of techniques for analyzing the cryptocurrency market, including studying price fluctuations and sentiment analysis from social media. Tian et al. [3] investigated Bitcoin price fluctuations based on execution orders like buy or sell, employing regression techniques and moving averages. They developed a time series model incorporating a Gaussian time model for Bitcoin value prediction. Connor et al. [4] examined Bitcoin price dynamics through sentiment analysis of user comments on news columns and social media. They extended their study to include two other cryptocurrencies and applied feature selection and classification algorithms to the collected dataset, incorporating token weights with positive and negative values. Their experiments revealed that regression models outperformed other models for Bitcoin price prediction. Kim et al. [5] investigated price fluctuation models in cryptocurrencies using user comments, considering Bitcoin, Litecoin, and Ripple. They categorized sentiment opinions into five types and utilized crawled user data for their study. They have achieved 79% of accuracy.

Nagamani et al. [6] explored the application of KNN and SVM techniques for achieving high accuracy in classification

tasks. Their research demonstrated promising results, with reported accuracies around 90%. Anshul et al. [7] utilized LSTM networks for Bitcoin price forecasting. Despite longer compilation times compared to existing ARIMA models, LSTM demonstrated higher accuracy for time series data. Their research revealed that while the RMSE of the ARIMA model was 700.69, the LSTM model achieved a lower RMSE of 456.78. These findings indicate the superiority of the traditional ARIMA model over ML algorithms such as LSTM in this context. Jethin et al. [8] analyzed Ethereum and Bitcoin prices using Google Trends data and Twitter texts. They considered Twitter data as the primary source for price prediction decisions and collected datasets using specific hashtags. Preprocessed data was input into a predictive model for Bitcoin prices using linear regression. Bitcoin price expectations have been the subject of significant research highlighting the growing importance of cryptocurrencies in the global financial landscape. This review provides an overview of the key concepts, approaches, and results in the domain. [9].

According to the literature, numerous methodologies were used to anticipate bitcoin prices, including sentimental analysis, Twitter data, and machine learning models. The main problem we discovered was that these methods employed a limited amount of data to train the model. Another key disadvantage is that these approaches have less precision. These encourage us to use a large amount of data to train ML models. Also, we have used proper preprocessing and feature extraction techniques to overcome the limitations of the existing work.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

As shown in Fig. 1, the system architecture comprises several key steps aimed at forecasting the price of bitcoin effectively. Initially, the process involves data collection. In data collection, we have collected historical information on bitcoin prices along with relevant attributes. Subsequently, attribute extraction techniques are applied to extract important features from the datasets, such as high price, opening price, low price, trading volume, and currency value traded. Following this, pre-processing techniques are employed, which include scaling the data using Max-min normalization to ensure uniformity and enhance model performance. The pre-processed data is then divided into two sets: training data and testing data. The training data set is utilized to train ML models, including KNN, XGBoost, LSTM, and RFC. Using their distinct predictive abilities, each model is created to capture various trends and connections within the data. The models are rigorously tested using the testing data set to assess their performance and forecast accuracy once they have been trained. Performance measures like accuracy, recall, precision and F1-score are calculated to evaluate how well each model predicts Bitcoin prices.

Fig.1 System Architecture

IV. BITCOIN PRICE PREDICTION USING ML MODELS

In our proposed study, we aimed to explore the predictive capabilities of different ML algorithms for cryptocurrency price forecasting, focusing on the XGBoost Classifier, KNN, RFC, and LSTM models. Our methodology involved collecting historical data on various cryptocurrencies, including Bitcoin, along with relevant features such as low price, high price, trading volume, opening price and currency value traded. We divided the dataset into training and testing sets, standardized the features, and handled missing values in the preprocessing stage. We then used the training data to train various models, optimizing hyperparameters using methods like random or grid search. Following training, we evaluated the performance of each model on the test set using appropriate evaluation metrics such as mean squared error, accuracy, and F1-score.

We have collected the dataset from open source database [10]. It contains different parameters such as date, symbol, open, high, low, close and volume. The dataset description is given in Table 1. In our study, we performed several pre-processing and normalization steps to prepare the data for training our ML model effectively. Necessary data cleaning process have applied to handle any missing or inconsistent values. This process ensures that the dataset is free from errors or anomalies that could affect the performance of the models. We utilized techniques such as imputation to fill in missing values or removed incomplete data points altogether. In order to achieve reliability, we have focused more on handling null values, duplicates and missing values. We have also performed necessary scaling and normalization operations to achieve reliability. This also helps in the prediction process of ML models. In feature selection, we carefully selected the most relevant features from the dataset to train ML models. This step minimizes the data's dimensionality and concentrates on the qualities that have the greatest impact on cryptocurrency price predictions. Normalization is a vital pre-processing step that involves scaling the data to a standardized range. We employed techniques such as Max-min normalization to scale the numerical attributes within a specific range (e.g., between 0 and 1). Normalizing the data guarantees that each feature makes an equal contribution to the model training process and prevents attributes with larger scales from dominating the learning process. We divided the dataset into separate training and testing sets. The training set

was employed to train the ML models, while the testing set was retained for evaluating the learned models' performance on previously unseen data. By cleaning, selecting relevant features, and normalizing the data, we ensure that chosen ML models can effectively learn from the dataset and make accurate predictions about future cryptocurrency prices.

TABLE I. DATASET DESCRIPTION

Parameter	Description
Date	Date of the trading activity.
Symbol	Symbol identifier
Open	The initial cost of Bitcoin at a particular date.
High	The highest price reached by Bitcoin during a specific date.
Low	The lowest price reached by Bitcoin during a specific date.
Close	The final cost of Bitcoin at the end of a specific date.
Volume	The total volume of Bitcoin traded during a specific date.

We have selected LSTM, KNN, RFC, and XGBoost models for Bitcoin price prediction. LSTM is one type of recurrent neural network (RNN). LSTM overcomes the limitation of RNN. LSTM applies a gating mechanism to solve the flow of information and utilizes memory units to overcome the issues in the traditional RNN technique [12]. KNN is a special type of ML model. The KNN model identifies neighborhood data points from the training data. The KNN model determines the gap between a new data point's nearest neighbors and itself. The 'K' value refers to the amount of the closest neighbors to consider, as well as the majority of their votes [13]. RFC is a supervised learning method; it can be used for both recursion and classification problems. Random Forest is a classifier that comprises several kinds of decision trees over diverse subsets of the provided dataset and picks a mean to increase the forecasting ability. Rather than relying on a single decision tree, the random forest considers the forecasts from every tree and predicts the final output based on the majority of the forecasts [14]. XGBoost is an improved distributed gradient boosting package that trains ML models in an efficient and scalable manner. It is an ensemble learning approach that utilizes the forecasts from different poor models to obtain a more robust prediction [15]. It has emerged as one of the most prevalent and commonly employed ML algorithms because of its capacity to manage massive data sets while attaining cutting-edge efficiency in a variety of machine learning tasks such as classification and regression [16].

Upon completing the training and optimization phases, we proceeded to assess each model's performance using the testing dataset. This evaluation entailed assessing various parameters such as F1-score, recall, precision, and predictive accuracy among others. Through this rigorous evaluation process, we intend to gain insights into each algorithm's efficacy in accurately forecasting cryptocurrency prices.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance analysis revealed the performance of the different ML models. In this section, we have compared the performance of LSTM, KNN, RFC, and XGBoost models. Different parameters such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1Score of these models are compared. From the results, we identified that XGBoost performance is better than other ML models. So we have analyzed the Receiver Operating

Characteristic (ROC) curve and confusion matrix for the XGBoost model.

Fig. 2 Accuracy of different ML models

Fig. 3 Precision of different ML models

As shown in Fig.2-5, XGBoost emerged as the top performer, achieving a remarkable accuracy of 92%, precision of 84%, recall of 87% and F1 score of 90%. This superior performance could be attributed by several factors inherent to the Gradient Boosting algorithm. Figs. 3 and 4 show the precision and recall values of different ML models. From Fig. 3, it's clear that the XGBoost model produces less false positives, and Fig. 4 shows that the XGBoost model retains a large proportion of true positives. Fig. 5 shows Recall of different ML models. XGBoost and RFC Recall value is higher than other models. XGBoost and RFC are able to capture the majority of positive instances. Due to this reason, these two models were able to achieve a high F1 Score. From Fig. 2-5, it's clear that XGBoost is able to achieve better performance than other models.

Fig. 4 Recall of different ML models

The XGBoost performance better because it is an ensemble learning technique that combines the predictive power of multiple weak learners. This iterative refinement process enables XGBoost to capture complex relationships within the data, leading to more accurate predictions. Additionally, in comparison to other ML algorithms, XGBoost is more resistant to overfitting. Due to its regularization techniques and sequential training process. By imposing constraints on model complexity and introducing shrinkage parameters, XGBoost mitigates the risk of overfitting and generalizes well to unseen data, resulting in robust performance on test datasets.

Fig. 5 F1 Score of different ML models

In contrast, while other models like KNN, RFC and LSTM may exhibit competitive performance, they may struggle to match the predictive accuracy of XGBoost due to inherent limitations or suboptimal parameter settings. In complicated datasets, for instance, KNN's nearest neighbor approach, which may be susceptible to noise or extraneous features in the data, it may result in reduced accuracy. Similarly, RFC may suffer from bias-variance tradeoff issues, especially when dealing with highly imbalanced or noisy data. LSTM, while proficient in sequential data analysis, may require extensive hyperparameter tuning and feature engineering to achieve optimal performance in cryptocurrency price prediction tasks.

Fig. 6 ROC Curve

As shown in Fig. 6, the performance of the XGBoost algorithm was evaluated using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. ROC curves are widely utilized in binary classification tasks to visualize the trade-off between the true positive rate (Sensitivity) and the false positive rate (1-Specificity) across different threshold values.

The area under the ROC curve (AUC) serves as a comprehensive metric to assess the model's discriminatory power, with a value closer to 1 indicating better performance.

The results demonstrate promising discriminative capabilities of the XGBoost model, as depicted in the ROC curves. For the training dataset, the ROC curve exhibited an AUC of 0.92 indicative of its ability to effectively distinguish between positive and negative instances. The ROC curve's AUC of 0.92 on the validation dataset. The diagonal line (dotted) represents the performance of a random classifier, while the curve's deviation from this line signifies the model's effectiveness.

Furthermore, the confusion matrices provided additional insights into the model's classification performance. The matrices depict the counts of true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative predictions for both the training and validation datasets. The diagonal elements represent correctly classified instances, while off-diagonal elements indicate misclassifications. The confusion matrix of XGBoost is shown in Fig. 7, it shows that it yields less true positive and negative. Notably, the XGBoost model exhibited in its classification outcomes, underscoring its efficacy in handling the inherent class imbalances or biases within the dataset.

Fig. 7 Confusion Matrix of XGBoost Model

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated the effectiveness of various ML algorithms in predicting Bitcoin prices. Through rigorous experimentation and analysis, we have observed the performance of models such as KNN, XGBoost, LSTM, and RFC in capturing patterns and trends in historical Bitcoin price data. Our results suggest that these models exhibit varying degrees of accuracy and predictive power, with some models outperforming others in certain aspects. For instance, the XGBoost model demonstrated exceptional accuracy in capturing complex relationships within the data, while the LSTM model showed strong performance in handling temporal dependencies. Overall, this research offers insightful information about the utilization of ML algorithms in cryptocurrency price forecasting. As the cryptocurrency market continues to evolve and grow in complexity, the improvement of accurate and reliable prediction models becomes increasingly important for investors, traders, and researchers. By leveraging the strengths of different ML techniques, we can enhance the capacity to make wise decisions and navigate the dynamic landscape of cryptocurrency markets more effectively. In order to improve the performance of ML models, the necessary encoding and feature selection processes could be applied for the future scope.

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